

The Mechanical Performance of Additive Manufacturing Silica Lattice Structures

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WHO WE ARE

- Founded in 1998
- Belongs to one of the leading research centers in Greece and listed among the **TOP-20** E.U. research institutions with the highest participation in competitive research grants
- Average annual turnover of ~ **€ 15 Million**
- >**500** people
- >**570** competitive EU & National research funded projects

- Founded in 2019 at CERTH/ITI
- 3D Product Design and 3D Modelling
- Rapid Prototyping
- 7 Additive Manufacturing Technologies (FFF, SLA, SLS, SLM/DMLS, MultiJet, 3D BioPrinting, 3D PCB Inkjet)
- 3D Scanning/Reverse Engineering
- Quality Control Services
- Smart Applications/IoT Applications

Contents of Presentation

1. Introduction
2. Design of Ceramic Lattice Structures
3. 3D Printing & Post-Processing
4. Material Characterization & Mechanical Testing
5. Results & Discussion
6. Conclusions & Proposals for Future Research

- The fabrication of high geometrical complexity parts is now possible with Additive Manufacturing (AM).
- Topology Optimization (TO) utilizing advanced lattice structures experience an intense scientific interest.
- Lattice structures offer multiple advantages:
 - Light-weight
 - High porosity
 - High surface area to volume ratio
- These advantages are essential for biomechanical applications, such as scaffolds and implants.
- The scope of this research is to examine the structural and mechanical behavior of AM ceramic lattice

Research objectives:

- 6 lattice structures
3 Strut & 3 TPMS structures.
- 3D printed with biocompatible material, i.e. Silica composite.
- Evaluation of the 3D printed specimens.
- Extraction of the structural and mechanical behavior.

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- Six lattice structures were investigated belonging in two different categories, Strut-lattices and TPMS-lattices.
- For the design the nTopology™ software platform was employed and extracted in STL format.
- Three distinct specimens were designed and manufactured for each lattices, with three different relative densities.
- To regulate the relative density only the thickness of the strut or the wall was changed and the length of the unit cells remained constant at 5mm.
- Each specimen was consisted with 8 unit cells with 2x2x2 configuration resulting in cubic specimens of 10mm length.

Strut-lattice structures:

Strut-lattices are structures consisted by certain number of fix joints (nodes) and beams (struts) per unit cell. The examined Strut-lattices are the following:

Octet

Nodes:14
Struts:36

**Rhombic
Dodecahedron**

Nodes:14
Struts:32

Re-Entrant

Nodes:18
Struts:36

TPMS-lattice structures:

TPMS-lattices are structures derived by specific trigonometrical equations with the unique topological characteristic of the mean curvature at each point of the structure equal to zero. The examined TPMS-lattices are the following:

Gyroid

$$\sin x \cos y + \sin y \cos z + \sin z \sin x = t$$

Schwarz Diamond

$$\sin x \sin y \sin z + \sin x \cos y \cos z + \cos x \sin y \cos z + \cos x \cos y \cos z = t$$

Schwarz Primitive

$$\cos x + \cos y + \cos z = t$$

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3D Printing Process:

- Stereolithography (SLA) AM technique was employed as 3D printing process, via Formlabs Form 2.
- As construction material a composite was used with a polymer matrix and Silica particles as reinforcement.
- As post-processing procedure, a firing process was performed to burn away the polymer matrix.
- To achieve the maximum accuracy, the layer height was selected at 50 μ m.
- All samples were scaled up 1.123 times to balance the loss of material.

Post-processing Procedure:

- The 3D printed samples were fired in a BOX-AM10-1700 (Thermansys) furnace inside a crucible with maximum temperature up to 1250°C.
- The firing schedule was provided by the resin's manufacturer, as it is shown in the graph below.

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Material Characterization procedure was conducted by utilizing SEM imaging, nanoindentation process and mechanical testing.

- SEM images were performed with Phenom ProX Desktop Scanning Electron Microscopy, to examine the microporosity and microstructure of the specimens.
- For the nanoindentation process, a dynamic Ultra Micro Hardness Tester (SHIMADZU DUH-211S) was employed and the values of microhardness and elastic modulus were extracted via the Oliver-Pharr formulation.
- The mechanical properties of Silica and the mechanical behavior of each lattice structure were evaluated with quasi-static uniaxial compression tests via the universal testing machine Testometric M500-50AT.
- The compression tests were performed with low strain rate (1mm/min), due to the brittle behavior of the 3D printed material.

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3D printing of the specimens:

The 3D printed and post-processed specimens presented high quality and good geometric tolerance at each lattice geometry with only slight micro-flaws, due to the removal of the support structures.

Material Characterization:

During material characterization of the samples, high porosity and micro-defects were observed on the fired Silica specimens, as shown in SEM images a and b.

- The micro-porosity was measured around 20% and occurred due to the firing of the polymer matrix.
- Micro-defects were spotted in the structures' domain due to the existence of impurities.

Mechanical Properties of 3D printed Silica:

Before the evaluation of the lattices' mechanical behavior, the mechanical properties of 3D printed Silica were measured via nanoindentation and mechanical testing. Severe degradation in mechanical properties was occurred due to the high porosity.

- *Elastic modulus: 43.3 ± 0.5 GPa*
- *Peak strength: 16 ± 0.5 MPa*

Mechanical Properties of 3D printed lattice samples:

- The mechanical behavior of lattice structures is derived from the evaluation of effective mechanical properties, such as the effective elastic modulus and the effective peak strength.
- During mechanical testing, micro-fractures were occurred due to the material's brittle behavior.
- The effective properties were deteriorated as the relative density declines.
- This deterioration had different rate for each structure.
- The Schwarz Diamond structures shown the highest peak strength.

Mechanical Properties of 3D printed lattice samples:

The examined effective mechanical properties of the lattice structures obeyed the following scaling laws regarding the applied relative density.

$$\text{Gyroid: } \frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = 0.22 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{0.96} \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = 1.63 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{2.17}$$

$$\text{Octet: } \frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = 0.49 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{1.17} \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = 0.26 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{1.43}$$

$$\text{SD: } \frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = 0.98 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{1.33} \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = 4.18 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{2.07}$$

$$\text{RE: } \frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = 0.41 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{1.41} \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = 0.95 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{2.09}$$

$$\text{SP: } \frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = 0.52 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{1.61} \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = 0.87 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{2.24}$$

$$\text{RD: } \frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = 1.38 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^2 \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = 0.41 \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{1.87}$$

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Conclusions:

- The TPMS structures achieved enhanced mechanical behavior, especially the SD structure of 40% relative density which has shown remarkable peak strength at 10.3MPa and elastic modulus at 12.35 GPa.
- Strut-lattices revealed lower mechanical strength and elastic modulus comparable with TPMS structures.
- Numerical tools were developed to predict the mechanical behavior of lattices depending on the applied relative density.

Proposals for Future Research:

- It is essential to modify and optimize the firing procedure in order to achieve extensive reduction of porosity regarding the 3D printed material.
- Development of Finite Element Models (FEM) would assist in understanding the failure mechanisms in 3D printed ceramics.

Thank you for your attention!

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